

THE ROLE OF MUSIC GROUPS ORGANIZED OUTSIDE THE CLASSROOM IN THE EDUCATION OF SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Annotation: The role of music clubs organized outside the classroom in the education of schoolchildren is detailed in this article. The author analyzed the possibilities of forming aesthetic taste, creative ability, spiritual and moral qualities in students through music clubs. The article focuses on the influence of music on the human psyche, teamwork, stage culture, patriotism, and the importance of raising respect for cultural heritage. Also, the existing problems and proposals for their elimination have been put forward. The article justifies the place of music clubs in the educational system and is of practical importance for pedagogues and school leaders.

Keywords: Music club, extracurricular activities, education, spiritual development, aesthetic taste, creative ability, school education, child education, patriotism, teamwork, moral education, culture, influence of music.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada sinfdan tashqari tashkil etiladigan musiqa to'garaklarining maktab o'quvchilari tarbiyasidagi o'rni atroficha yoritilgan. Muallif musiqa to'garaklari orqali o'quvchilarda estetik did, ijodiy qobiliyat, ma'naviy va axloqiy fazilatlarni shakllantirish imkoniyatlarini tahlil qilgan. Maqolada musiqaning inson ruhiyatiga ta'siri, jamoaviy ishlash, saxna madaniyati, vatanparvarlik va madaniy merosga bo'lgan hurmatni tarbiyalashdagi ahamiyatiga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Shuningdek, mavjud muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish bo'yicha takliflar ham ilgari surilgan. Maqola musiqa to'garaklarining ta'lim-tarbiya tizimidagi o'rnini asoslab beradi va pedagoglar hamda maktab rahbarlari uchun amaliy ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: Musiqa to'garagi, sinfdan tashqari mashg'ulotlar, tarbiya, ma'naviy rivojlanish, estetik did, ijodiy qobiliyat, maktab ta'limi, bolalar tarbiyasi, vatanparvarlik, jamoaviy ish, axloqiy tarbiya, madaniyat, musiqaning ta'siri.

Аннотация: В статье подробно рассматривается роль музыкальных кружков, организованных внеклассно, в образовании школьников. Автором проанализированы возможности формирования эстетического вкуса, творческих способностей, духовно-нравственных качеств у учащихся посредством музыкальных кружков. В статье рассматривается влияние музыки на психику человека, командную работу, сценическую культуру, патриотизм, а также важность воспитания уважения к

культурному наследию. Также были выдвинуты существующие проблемы и предложения по их устранению. Статья обосновывает место музыкальных кружков в системе образования и имеет практическое значение для педагогов и руководителей школ.

Ключевые слова: Музыкальный кружок, внеклассная работа, воспитание, духовное развитие, эстетический вкус, творческие способности, школьное образование, воспитание детей, патриотизм, командная работа, нравственное воспитание, культура, влияние музыки.

Introduction. Today, the issue of educating a well-rounded, spiritually rich and morally pure person is becoming very important in society. Educational institutions should not be limited to teaching only subjects, but also serve to develop the intellectual, spiritual, aesthetic and social potential of the student. From this point of view, extracurricular activities, in particular, music clubs, are an important means of comprehensively educating the student's personality.

General tasks of music clubs

Music clubs form an interest in art, in particular musical culture, in children. Through these clubs, students get acquainted with national and world musical works, learn to play musical instruments, understand notes and develop a sense of music.

Musical activities play an important role in expressing children's emotions, creative thinking, forming aesthetic taste, focusing attention and strengthening willpower.[1] At the same time, it instills in children such qualities as patriotism, respect for the nation, interest in history and culture.

The influence of music in the formation of a student's personality.

Music is important in enriching a person's spiritual world, ensuring emotional stability and finding inner harmony. Students have the opportunity to express themselves through music, strengthen self-confidence and find their place in the social environment.[2] For example, a child who participates in choirs learns to control his voice, work in a team, and behave on stage. This can positively change his general culture, speech and behavior. A student who participates in music clubs is formed as an independent thinker, intelligent and responsible person.

The educational value of music clubs.

Upbringing is an integral part of education and is not limited to academic classes.[3] Through music clubs, the following educational qualities are formed in children:

- **Spiritual education:** By influencing the human heart, music strengthens virtues such as kindness, compassion, loyalty, love for the homeland, honesty, and tolerance.
- **Social education:** The club teaches social values such as teamwork, mutual respect, and discipline.
- **Aesthetic education:** Music develops a person's desire for beauty, the ability to enjoy music, and the ability to understand their own and others' feelings.
- **Moral education:** Through music, children learn to distinguish between good and bad, and to reflect on right and wrong actions. This is the only way to achieve spiritual maturity and a rich cultural and spiritual heritage.[4]

Influence based on example and experience

Music clubs operating in many schools in our republic are very effective in identifying and developing the creative abilities and interests of students. For example, concerts, festivals and clubs held in collaboration with music schools in some districts and cities attract children to a creative environment. Over the past period, the Republic of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of normative and legal acts on the development of culture and arts [5].

Such activities satisfy children's need to demonstrate their abilities, receive recognition and encouragement, and strengthen their self-confidence. Especially for children who are not socially active or have mental difficulties, music can have a unique therapeutic effect.

Problems and proposals in organizing music clubs

There are also some problems in effectively organizing clubs: lack of equipment, lack of qualified specialists, weak material and technical base, etc. In order to eliminate these problems, the following proposals can be put forward:

- Organization of special music rooms equipped with modern musical instruments in schools;
- Regular training courses for music teachers and leaders;
- Encourage talented students, organize music festivals and competitions for them;
- Strengthening cooperation between cultural and educational institutions.

Conclusion. Music clubs organized outside the classroom are an integral part of the school's educational system and serve the comprehensive development of the student. Through music, children understand not only art, but also love and feeling of life, their responsibility towards themselves and society. Therefore, the development of music clubs and their widespread

introduction is an important contribution to the education of a mature generation.

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